

National Policies to Combat Social Spatial Inequalities: Slovakia

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Introduction

This paper preparation was supported by the HORIZON 2020 SOLIDUS project: Spatial dimension of solidarity: from local to transnational acts & practices. The goal of this study is to provide the picture about existing spatial inequalities in Slovakia and responses to them on all levels of governmental policy.

The paper includes following main parts – brief description of main spatial inequalities in the country and the characteristics of main policies to combat inequalities in Slovakia on all levels of government, with focus on four selected areas - housing, unemployment, health and education.

1. Main inequalities in Slovakia

The issue of regional inequalities (disparities) in Slovakia was in depth investigated recently by the group of experts from academia. One of sources is the publication Michálek and Podolák (2014) – edited volume that includes many articles dealing with the topic.

In the study “Dynamics of regional disparities in Slovakia before and after the economic crises and their solution using selected regional policy instruments” (pp. 63-99) the authors (Kvetoslava Matlovičová, Anna Židová, Jana Kolesárová) studied 19 indicators, while each of them was given equal weight: unemployment rate, social benefits (other than social transfers in kind) per capita, average monthly wage, net cash monthly income per capita, net cash monthly costs per capita, incomes of the health insurance companies from the insurance payments per capita, foreign direct investment per capita, dwellings completed per thousand inhabitants, gross fixed capital per capita, enterprises with 250 or more employees per 1000 inhabitants, profit-oriented organisations per 1000 inhabitants, individual businesses per 1000 inhabitants, regional GDP per capita, net disposable income per capita, expenditures on research and development, current taxes on income, wealth, etc. per capita, legal entities per 1000 inhabitants, corporations per 1000 inhabitants, and cooperatives per 1000 inhabitants.

The study “Regional disparities in Slovakia within the context of EU cohesion policy 2007-2013 (authors Eva Rajčáková, Angelika Švecová, pp. 101-126) analysed regional disparities of Slovakia in three fields – Infrastructure and regional accessibility, Knowledge economy and Human resources.

The study “The level of regional disparities in Slovakia and its changes in 2001-2011” (authors Michala Madajová, Anton Michálek, Peter Podolák, pp.127-152) used 14 indicators. The conclusions of this study are representative for all findings: “The results confirm the repeatedly found distinct regional difference between what is referred to as the problem macro-region of southern and eastern Slovakia on the one side and advanced regions in the northern and western parts of the country. Simultaneously the assertions concerning progressive stabilisation of regional patterns and weakening selective tendencies were denied. Results show that there was no regional convergence

taking place in Slovakia in the decade in question although some signs of it are observable in slight mitigation of differences between the most advanced regions. They confirmed the fact that the basic trend in regional development in Slovakia was divergence. The found facts contradict the declared and supported efforts of responsible state institutions and EU bodies about the need to balance interregional differences”.

Slovakia has very rich region – Bratislava, but also rather poor areas from the point of view of any potential indicator. Such areas are even better visible on local level – poor districts (like Poltar, Hnusta and Rimavska Sobota in central part and almost all in East) and poor settlements (especially in Central and Eastern Slovakia there exist separated Roma villages, below any acceptable standard).

2. Policies to combat inequalities in Slovakia

In this part we describe main policies and actions prepared and delivered with the aim to reduce different spatial inequalities in Slovakia. The first part deals with the national level general policies and the second part with selected branch policies.

2. 1 National level: general policies

The left wing government (Prime Minister Fico) recently introduced the first “social package” with the aim to help to socially vulnerable groups and is preparing the second one. The first “package” approved in June 2014 included following planned and already introduced measures: specific support to start-ups, payment of VAT only after the invoice is paid by customer, decreasing prices of gas for families, free train tickets for students and retired, decreasing social contributions for working students, more money for assistants to disabled students, tax benefits for specific employers, tax benefits to compensate research and development expenses, increasing minimum wage, decrease of social contributions for low income groups, minimum pension, increasing of Christmas allowance for retired, allowing for simultaneous receiving of salary and social benefits for people in needs and increased capacities of nursing and kindergarten sector. According to the statements of the Prime Minister and the Minister of Finance the implementation of all above measures did not have any negative impact on fiscal stability.

The second “package” was announced in autumn 2015 (third package promised). The measures for the second one are as follows – decreasing VAT for basic food items from 20 % to 10 %, further increase of the minimum wage (400 EUR), increasing maternity benefits, increasing benefits for child care by parents, further increase of capacities of kindergartens, building of simple school buildings in deprived areas, special support for pupils to cover costs of swimming and skiing courses, providing low costs holiday capacities for socially vulnerable in state capacities of the Ministry of Interior and Ministry of Defence, allocation special funds for reconstruction of state owned hospitals, special support for renewable energy sources, introducing of social bank account with very low fee for the package of basic bank services, specific VAT regime in the building industry. Probably the most comprehensive measure is proposing of the new law (already in the Parliament) regulating and providing support to socially deprived regions. According to the draft law, districts with high level of unemployment will be entitled for more forms of economic help – especially by allocation extra public investments, building of the road infrastructure, support for creation of new working places and sustainability of existing jobs and improved administrative services.

For sure, not all of above mentioned measures focus directly on solving of spatial inequalities, but some of them, especially the new law on support of deprived regions play or have potential to play very important role.

2. 2 Branch policies

As indicated, this part introduces existing national branch policies in all five areas selected by the SOLIDUS project: health (with focus on health care), education, housing and employment.

Health - Health care

Because real health is very difficult to measure (indicators like mortality or life expectancy do not say much), we focus on health care policy in this part.

The general trends of health policy in Slovakia after 1989 were defined by Programmatic Statements of Government and main reform documents (first of them published in 1990). The most important goals are very much constant and are as follows:

- Creation of a system of “health care for everybody” (system of public health).
- The guarantee of “needed” scope of health care to everybody (universal access to defined scope of health services and benefits).
- The basis of creation, realisation and control of health policy shall be free decision of citizens.
- Cancellation of a state monopoly in health care, plurality of provision of health care, privatisation, increased participation of self-government in health care system.
- Public health shall be dominant part of a health care system.
- Dominant position of primary care in health care system.
- The right of citizen to choose provider.
- Compulsory health insurance.
- Citizen’s participation in relation to protection and improvement of its own health.
- Multi-resource financing of health care.
- Improved economic and financial management in health care establishments.
- To stop an impairment of health status of citizens.

However, already from 1994 one more dimension is permanently present - to realise effective measures to solve financial crisis of Slovak health care.

Like most CEE countries Slovakia switched to the so-called “Bismarck” system of social health insurance to replace old general taxation system of financing health care. However, together with the Czech Republic, it decided to introduce a competitive/pluralistic social health insurance system as well. (Most CEE countries started with only one public health insurance company.) The main laws on health insurance were passed in 1994, which created the base for establishing health insurance companies (two of them public). Most of these have since disappeared from the “market”; in 2002 five existed but by 2015 only two private and one public remained.

The main principle of the Slovak healthcare system is that it formally guarantees universal and equal access to all health services, regardless of the patient’s residence or ability to pay (in practice, however, this principle is impossible to achieve).

In reality fully universal and equal access is impossible, however to come as close as possible to it, the legislation includes important elements to guarantee physical access to all types of healthcare services. In the next text we introduce three of them – two with positive impact, one with disputable impact on equality.

The existing legislation requires a “minimum network of healthcare providers”. Such minimum networks should be established in outpatient and inpatient care. The Health Care Act (576/2004) defines the minimum network for inpatient and outpatient care as “a minimum number of publicly accessible providers on the territory of a regional self-government set by the number and structure of providers necessary to effectively guarantee accessible, continual, and permanent professional health care, reflecting the number of inhabitants, the geographic and demographic specifics of the region, the mortality and morbidity indicators of the territory, migration, and state security”. Regions are responsible for guaranteeing such minimum network and the system works relatively well – most of Slovak citizen have fully acceptable travel times to all levels of health care (including highly specialised care, which is allocated not only in capital Bratislava).

In the area of emergency services the Law on Emergency Services (579/2004) stipulates that every citizen has the right to emergency service within 15 minutes regulates access to emergency care. To achieve this, emergency cars are available in 280 places on the whole Slovak territory – also this system works very well.

The third, less successful policy is very recent – after the “Zajac” health care reform in 2004 the system of co-payments and fees was formally introduced into the system. No consecutive government was able to connect it with the effective system of co-insurance and all such fees shall be paid in cash. This is very politically sensitive and the left wing government of the Prime Minister Fico always promised abolishing such fees to the citizen (because they create inequalities). The last legislative measure in this direction was adopted in 2015, when fees allowing for priority appointment were formally prohibited. The results from abolishing fees are controversial:

- first, the level of private payments in health care did not decrease (about 30 % of private payments, outside of insurance system), thus the financial burden is still here and may cause inequalities,
- second, because of large scale shadow economy, abolishing any fee normally ends with converting it to new one or to unofficial financial flows.

Despite to the fact, that formally the Slovak system strictly focuses on universality and equality, in reality, as in all countries, rich people and people with “connections” can get better and faster care compared to other (who still receive relatively high level services, fortunately). The only vulnerable group are employed people (self-employed in most cases) who do not pay their insurance premiums – this group is eligible only for emergency care (health insurance companies databases include about 500 000 of people, who did not pay in time – whose employer did not pay in time, in most cases this is short term problem).

Employment

The main responsible body is the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic. Its task is to continually modernize labour legislation with the aim of increasing employment. It strives to create a balanced labour market while equally providing protection for employees and fulfilling the requests of employers. The Section of Labour of the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic establishes the measures oriented on increasing employment by assisting job seekers, employees and employers. Protecting employees at their workplaces and combating illegal work and employment are significant parts of its work.

It assists labour market participants who are looking for work or changing jobs while also filling job vacancies through its system of measures and institutions. This pertains to employment service providers that assist and support job seekers, job applicants and employees through active labour market measures, namely:

- job mediation,

- professional counselling services,
- job training and preparation, and
- contributions.

Employment services are provided by the state providers (Central Office of Labour, Social Affairs and Family, Local Labour Office, Social Affairs and Family) and non-state providers (legal entities and natural persons carrying out job mediation for a fee must have a licence for such activities issued pursuant to the Trade Licensing Act, temporary employment agencies employ persons on a temporary basis according to the needs of employers, sheltered employment agencies provide employment services to the disabled, the long-term unemployed and their potential employers).

The Office of Labour, Social Affairs and Family implements active labour market measures targeted on the support of job creation and sustenance and the development of local and regional employment. Assistance is provided in the form of the following contributions.

Contributions Provided to Employers

- Work preparation and training of employees
- Contribution to support the employment of disadvantaged job seekers
- Contribution to support job retention
- Contribution for commuting to work

Contributions to Support the Employment of Persons with Disabilities

- Contribution for establishing a sheltered workshop or workplace
- Contribution for retaining the employment of a person with a disability
- Contribution for activities of an assistant at work
- Contribution to cover the operating costs of a sheltered workshop or workplace and transportation costs of employees

Contributions Provided to Local Governments

- Contribution to support the development of local and regional employment
- Contribution for activation programmes in the form of minor services for the municipality or self-governing region

Formally, the Slovak Republic implements comprehensive set of the active labour market policies, however their impact on employment level inequalities according to the regional structure are still rather limited. In areas where both effective supply of jobs and effective supply of qualified work by unemployed dominate, the level of unemployment remains very high (see inserted Figure 1).

Figure 1: Territorial levels of unemployment in Slovakia (31. 8. 2015) – UPSVAR Bratislava

Miera evidovanej nezamestnanosti v okresoch SR k 31.08.2015

Ústredie práce, sociálnych vecí a rodiny, Bratislava

Miera evidovanej nezamestnanosti prepočítaná na základe výberových zisťovaní ŠÚSR a priemerného počtu uchádzačov o zamestnanie v roku 2014. Algoritmus výpočtu stanovilo MPSVR SR

Housing

Owner - occupied housing in Slovakia has become the most prevalent form of housing at the beginning of 1990s. In 1993 the process of transforming housing tenures in Slovakia had begun. Firstly, the right of personal use of flats was transformed into a lease, secondly, the tenants acquired a right to buy the flats and the adjacent plot. The conditions for the acquisition of ownership were in favour of former tenants, mainly because of mandatory rules on the calculation of prices.

Results of the Censuses of Population and Housing conducted in 2011 have discovered that the total number of dwellings in the Slovak Republic amounts to 1,994,897 units situated in 1,070,790 houses (either family houses or blocks of flats). Across the country in each region, majority of houses are family houses. Altogether it is 969,360 houses, i.e. 90.5% of all houses in Slovakia. In comparison to their number, there is 64.846 blocks of flats in Slovak Republic and their share on available houses is 6.1%.

Figure2 : Family houses and blocks of flats in regions of the SR in %
 Source: Population and Housing Census 2011

Out of the total number of occupied dwellings, owner-occupied housing in Slovakia is the most prevalent form of housing with 84.9%. Owner-occupied housing is generally intended for housing of middle and higher income groups.

Rental housing in Slovakia is one of the key issues that need to be addressed, both in terms of its technical state and affordability. According to the Census 2011 1.8% of the flats was owned by municipalities. In countries of the European Union, the share of rental housing ranges from 19% to 62%, while the public rental sector represents 18% of the housing stock. These facts clearly indicate that access to rental housing in Slovakia is very limited, so it is necessary to pay attention to its development, both in the public rental sector as well as in the private rental sector.

Public rental sector should serve primarily to ensure social housing, and therefore should be available to such people who cannot satisfy their housing needs on the open market. For this reason, this sector should operate on the principle of non-profit management, so that such housing is affordable. Rents in this sector should cover all costs associated with the acquisition and operation of rental housing, while respecting the principle of the lowest possible cost

The private rental sector is underdeveloped, mainly as a result of the previous application of the rental price regulation, as well as of over-protecting tenants under existing civil tenancy arrangements. This sector should ensure the supply of housing especially in terms of labour mobility and flexibility for those people who need more short-term solutions to their housing needs. Rents in this sector should be regulated in the future by setting a price ceiling. The creation of new housing units should be supported by the state mainly by indirect economic instruments.

In this context, in the coming period, there is a need to completely resolve the issue of the relationship of private owners and tenants of flats, not only the levels of rent but also the range of eligible tenants. From this perspective, it is necessary in the upcoming season of the new codification of the Civil Code to maintain the institution of a protected tenancy, but with a balance in the position of owners and tenants.

According to the "Concept of State Housing Policy until 2015" approved by the Slovak government on 3rd February 2010 changes in the intentions of the Government approved Legislative Intent of the Civil Code should primarily tackle the transfer of the lease in the case of lessee's death, replacement

housing, housing allowances and termination of tenancy by landlord's notice. These factors limit the owner's freedom in the disposal of his/her property and allow the persistence of the negative effects of the previously applied, untargeted social regulation of rental flats.

For these reasons, the Ministry of Transportation, Construction and Regional Development had previously proposed to support the creation of a public rental sector through direct subsidies from the state budget as well as favourable loans through the Housing Development Fund. Subsidies for rental housing are currently provided by the Subsidies for Housing Development and Social Housing Act (No. 443/2010 Coll.).

The Concept also points out the task of preparing a draft legal framework for the implementation of new economic instruments to stimulate state investors in the development of the private rental sector. A small and an insufficient number of affordable rental housing is a serious obstacle to the mobility of labour and there is a lack of housing solutions, especially for young families. In the current situation, the Ministry proposes to address this area by introducing the ability to provide effective construction loans to legal entities for the construction of rental housing in the forthcoming State Housing Development Fund Act.

Currently, in several regions of Slovakia an on-going process of suburbanization has been identified. A number of communities, which can potentially move to suburban municipalities, are located in the suburbs of the largest Slovak towns, which are now the administrative centres of the region. The process of suburbanization in Slovak towns is more pronounced in the western part of the country (where there are also larger towns) and retreating towards the east. First there are the western and northern regions of Slovakia, which are the most urbanized. In Bratislava (the capital) and populated urban areas the actual supply of housing units is theoretically sufficient; however, the supply of newly built housing units gradually falls short of the requirements on floor area, number of rooms and locations as perceived by the demand side of the housing market.

However, young families with children migrate to rural villages in the suburbs of towns in Slovakia. They have a higher social status, which is characterized by higher educational attainment and higher incomes than the native population of rural villages in the suburbs of towns. A part of the population moving to suburbs is persons who had previously lived there. People who move to rural communities give the following reasons for their decision: a good location of the village with regards to the location of the town (good road access), housing reasons (housing affordability), and a healthier environment than in the city.

In the recent period the share of population living in cities and villages has not changed significantly (54.4% of inhabitants living in cities in 2011 in comparison to 56.2% of them in 2001 and 56.8% in 1991). On the other hand, number of villages has increased from 2689 in 1991 to 2752 in 2011 (this may be also partly influenced by the administrative changes of territory).

Slovakia is perceived to have rather high regional disparities by international standards. It has significant divergences in the regional markets of residential dwellings, which naturally implies comparable divergences in the rental market, e.g. the average prices of residential housing units in 2012 varied from 602 EUR/m² in the Nitra region to 999 EUR/m² in the Košice region, up to 1662 EUR/m² in the Bratislava region.

State Housing Policy sets out the basic aims and objectives of housing policy and housing development not only for the Slovak population in general but also for smaller parts of the population - **groups at risk of social exclusion** (people who, due to low levels of education and capable of performing only occasional, odd jobs, eventually become unemployed; people with physical or mental disabilities; youth from institutional or protective care; the elderly; families with many children; single parents with children who find themselves in need of social help because of loss of family environment) and **marginalized groups** (loss of residence, long-term unemployment, drug dependency, lack of social adaptability, membership of a particular ethnic group in regions with

high unemployment). In terms of all social indicators, including housing, the most numerous and specific marginalized group in Slovakia are Roma (Gypsy) communities.

Education

The Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic is the central body of the state administration of the Slovak Republic for elementary, secondary and higher education, educational facilities, lifelong learning, science and for the state's support for sports and youth.

The compulsory schooling takes ten years and lasts until the end of the school year in which the pupil attains the age of 16. Compulsory school attendance starts at the age of 6 year. The system of schools comprises the following schools:

1. kindergarten (nursery)
2. elementary school,
3. grammar school,
4. secondary vocational school,
5. conservatory,
6. schools for children and students with special educational and training needs,
7. elementary art school,
8. language school.

The public administration in education is guaranteed by both the State administration and territorial self-governance, which is executed by municipalities and higher territorial units. As indicated, the central body of state administration in education is the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic, which develops educational aims, content and methods for education. Local administration is the responsibility of municipalities, which provide most of pre-primary, primary and lower secondary education in Slovakia.

Public schools (also on the university level) provide education free of charge – with this education is area with very minor inequality level in Slovakia – especially from the point of chance. Two issues, however, should be mentioned:

a/ Small municipalities - in location at where no conditions have been created for establishment of all nine grades of the primary school (at least 150 children), it is possible to establish a primary school with the first grades only (for at least 30 children). Pupils, who complete the last year of an incomplete organized school, continue in the fulfilment of compulsory school attendance in the complete organized primary school which has nine grades. Because of lack of pupils and lack of finance, schools disappeared from some small municipalities – and the system of transport of pupils to large neighbours is not fully functional (this issue is partly addressed centrally by special grants to small schools, but the main responsibility is on municipal level).

b/ Difficult to educate pupils, especially pupils from socially disadvantaged areas – this issues is reflected by partly successful policies – strict supervision of the duty to register the child for education (100 % of children is registered for school education in Slovakia, also because without registration the parents lose all public social benefits), subsidized catering in schools for socially vulnerable groups, assistants to teachers to help with hard to educate pupils (about 1000 assistants, especially for Roma children), zero-classes (possibility to expand first year curriculum into two years for some pupils – about 2000 pupils every year) and special support to Roma students at secondary schools.

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